

TYOLOGY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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ANNOTATION

This article talks about the typology of phraseological units, that is, the analysis using scientific methods of dividing the system of objects into parts and grouping them using a generalized model or type, the types of phraseological compounds, the opinions expressed by famous linguists about them.

Keywords: Phraseological, positional, equivalent, lexical, lexicology, concept, semantic, expressive, equivalence theory, stable, repetitive.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada frazeologik birliklarning tipologiyasi, ya'ni obyektlar tizimini qismlarga ajratish va ularni umumlashma model yoki tip yordamida guruhlashtirishdan iborat ilmiy metodlardan foydalangan holda tahlil qilish, frazeologik birikmalarni turlari, ular haqida mashhur tilshunos olimlar bildirgan fikrlar haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Frazеologik, pozitsiya, ekvivalent, leksik, leksikologiya, tushuncha, semantik, ekspressiv, tenglik nazariyasi, turg'un, takrorlanuvchi.

Phraseology is a branch of linguistics that studies the current state and historical development of the phraseology system. Phraseological units are the subject of the study of phraseology. As a branch of linguistics, phraseology is engaged in the study of categorical signs of phraseological units, on the basis of which the main signs of phraseology are distinguished and the question of the essence of phraseological units as special units of speech is solved. It is also important to determine the laws of expressive units in speech and the processes of their formation. Despite the fact that there are many studies on the main issues of phraseology, there is still no unified approach to determining the phraseological unit of speech.

There are many definitions of the term "phraseological unit". According to Mokienko, a phraseological unit is a relatively stable, repetitive, expressive combination of lexemes with a unified meaning.

Because phraseology units are recognized as language units along with words and morphemes, some researchers include phraseology units in the language dictionary, and phraseology units are considered word equivalents. Therefore, the theory of phraseological units equal to words deserves special attention. This goes back to the theory of expressive fact-finding developed by Charles

Bally, who argued that one of the most common signs of phraseology surpassing all others is the possibility or impossibility of replacing a plain word with a plain word. that's a twist. Charles Bally called such a word "word identity". The existence of such a synonym is considered by Charles Bally to be an internal sign of the integrity of phraseology units. This point of view raises certain objections. As Zhukov noted, "It is impossible to establish the semantic integrity of a phraseological unit in this way, since even variable combinations of words can contain synonymous words."

Two directions are noted in the problem "phraseologism and the word": lexicological understanding of phraseology as a component of lexicology, phraseological units as equivalent to words, and a broad understanding of phraseology as a science in its own right. Some proponents of the full equivalence theory consider phraseological units to be lexical units that require special classification and should be classified in the same way words are. K.I.Smirnitsky introduces phraseology into lexicology. He regards phraseological units as "word equivalents".

The equality of phraseological units with words is that "the phraseological unit has two properties characteristic of a typical word: semantic integrity and its presence in speech as a finished unit repeated in speech." In addition, the scientist notes that phraseological units can be included in the domain of vocabulary, "but it is more correct to distinguish the system of phraseological units as a separate field in the lexical system of language". Thus, the separate formation of phraseological units is an important difference from the whole word, which is characterized by their integral formation. The main feature that distinguishes phraseological units from words and phrases that occur in the course of speech is idiomatics. At the same time, it must be borne in mind that "phraseological units should be distinguished from a special type of idioms, which can be called appropriate idioms".

In her works, N.N.Amosova doubts the theory of equivalence of phraseological units with words, emphasizing "the relative equivalence of phraseological units with words and even different degrees of this relative equivalence depending on the type of phraseological units".

Phraseological turns are such language units that have certain differential properties with a certain proximity to words and free word combinations:

1) these are ready-made speech units that do not arise in the process of communication, but generally come from the memory of the speakers;

2) these are linguistic units characterized by constancy of meaning, content and structure;

3) from an accentological point of view, as well as sound complexes, the components of which have two or more main stresses;

4) These are formations divided into parts, the components of which are perceived by speakers as words.

Phraseological units are therefore only units that share the properties listed. Thus "any meaningful unit consisting of two or more accented components of a verbal sign, repeated in complete form, is a phraseology unit."

Therefore, based on the analysis of the views of various scholars, we believe that the equivalence of phraseology units to words can be recognized from the point of view of their relationship to speech and speech; Phraseologism and word are language units used as nominative units in speech.

The main features of phraseology. In order to distinguish phraseology units from other language units, especially words and free phrases, it is necessary to determine the specific properties of phraseology units.

1. Repetition of phraseology units in speech as complete units. Fixed combinations exist in language as a collection of previously formed language combinations that we need to remember, just as we remember words.

2. The integrity of the meaning of phraseology units That they have a generalized-holistic meaning despite the division of the structure is usually a revision of the phrase due to a specific semantic content. Stable compounds, one of which is obsolete and not used in modern language outside of that phrase, serve as good examples that the meaning of a phraseology does not consist of the values of its components. However, the speaker is not unfamiliar with this word because he knows the common, inseparable meaning of all linguistic units. Generalized - integral meaning are also expressions in which the relationship between the general meaning of a stable combination and the values of its components can be observed.

3. Consistency and stability of component structure distinguish phraseological units from free phrases. A distinctive feature of stable connections is that they are usually permanent and structural, i.e. they contain certain words arranged in a fixed order. The exchange of the components of phraseology units occurs only in linguistic variants, i.e. in stable compounds that have the same meaning, have the same figurative structure, but differ in lexical and grammatical content.

4. The equivalence of phraseology and a word means that a stable connection has much in common with a word. This linguistic unit is repeated like a word in

its finished form and is not created anew each time, has its own meaning and grammatical context, which means that the linguistic unit, like a word, belongs to a certain part of speech. Nominal phraseological expressions can be distinguished (a sparrow shot is an experienced person), adjectives (there are not enough stars in the sky - about an ordinary, unrecognizable person) verbs (fall into a dead state - stay in a difficult situation) ; adverbial (tireless, diligent, tireless), mixed (do you know ours! - praise about yourself). Many phraseological units correspond to one word (carry both shoulder blades - win). Stative phrases are similar to words in a syntactical task in that they play the role of a single member of sentences.

5. The separation of phraseology units is that it consists of at least two verbal components, each of which is grammatically delimited as an independent unit, that is, has a stress and an ending. This is the main difference between phraseology and word.

6. Phraseological image It consists in the fact that many stable expressions not only name events, symptoms, objects, actions, but also contain a certain image. This is primarily due to the similarity and comparison of two phenomena, the meanings of which are formed on the basis of linguistic metaphors, one of which is the basis of comparison, and the other refers to expressive units compared with it. For example, in phraseology, grated Kalacha, that is, an experienced person who has seen a lot in life, corresponds to grated Kalacha (one of the varieties of Kalacha), grated for a long time before cooking. This creates the imagination of phraseology. Some expressive units of the Russian language lack imagination. These include various semantically inseparable compounds, which include compound names and terms (e.g. coal, agenda, safety pin, glasses) as well as linguistic units belonging to the type of substance.

7. Emotional coloring of expression Phraseological units are manifested by the fact that most of the phraseological units in the Russian language, in addition to the nominative function, perform a characteristic function: they not only name some objects, events, actions that exist together in objective reality, at the same time they evaluate them mentioned objects, events, actions. The emotional and expressive meaning of phraseology units in the Russian language is different. Some of them have a minimal expression (expression), for example: stand in your ears - "always heard". Others have clear pronunciation and serve to emphasize the value being expressed. For example, hitting with a key - "violent flow, manifestation." The presence of expression units in the process of

emotional expression coloring can be seen as synonymous expression units that have a common meaning and can have different colors.

The main feature of phraseologisms is their wholly or partially rethought meaning. Some lexemes have only part of the phraseological units defined, but most can only be defined by a phrase or a detailed description. The semantic peculiarity of the phraseology unit lies in the uniqueness of the combination of components such that they function not only as the main semantic components of the phraseology unit, but also as connecting links between them. These constituents are the minimal units of the semantics of phraseological units and fulfill meaning-determining or meaning-giving functions.

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